
The Crucial Roles of Geospatial Techniques in the COVID-19 Fight: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT: The Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) appeared in Wuhan, China, at the end of 2019, spreading from there across China and the whole world. Such advanced technologies as geospatial techniques have been applied to fight the rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2. This paper aims to review and synthesize the types of applications offered through geospatial techniques to help address different issues related to the fight of the COVID-19 pandemic. The content is presented under four sub-sections; namely the roles of GIS, Remote Sensing, Global Positioning System and Internet Mapping Technologies in the fight of the COVID-19 pandemic. It was found from summarising 73 scientific papers, geospatial techniques have been proven their effectiveness not only in the study of COVID-19 in general, but also in the fight of the pandemic in particular. The wide range of applications offered by geospatial techniques affirms the value of this technique to the COVID-19 fight.

KEYWORDS: Applications, Geospatial techniques, GIS, Remote Sensing, GPS, COVID-19, Review.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2019 a respiratory disease caused by the Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) led to a pandemic that had a profound impact on global society (1,2). The COVID-19 pandemic has been described as a social, human, and economic crisis. As of 01 July 2023, a total of 768,560,728 confirmed cases of COVID-19 including 6,952,522 deaths were reported to World Health Organization (3). It is, therefore, attempts on the use of such advanced technologies as geospatial techniques are needed in fight the COVID-19 pandemic. Geospatial technologies is a term used to describe the range of modern tools contributing to the geographic mapping and analysis of the Earth and human societies (4). There are now a variety of types of geospatial technologies potentially applicable to human rights, including Geographic Information Systems (GIS), remote sensing, Global Positioning System (GPS) and Internet Mapping Technologies (5). These geospatial technologies have been widely applied in the field of management of natural resources (6), environment (7) and climate change (8). Particularly in recent years, geospatial technologies have been successfully used in studies of epidemiology (9–11) and disease (12–14). This paper aims to give an overview of four types of applications offered by geospatial technologies to help address different issues related to the COVID-19 fight. The content is presented under four sub-sections; namely the roles of GIS, Remote Sensing, Global Positioning System and Internet Mapping Technologies in the fight of the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

In this study, a total of 73 scientific papers collected from Web of Science, SCOPUS, and Google scholar databases was used. These were mostly high impact and were mainly published in recent years after the COVID-19 outbreak.

2.2. Methods

We firstly queried Web of Science, Google Scholar, and SCOPUS databases with different combinations of keywords including 'applications', 'Geospatial techniques', 'GIS' or 'Geographic Information System', 'remote sensing', 'GPS' or 'GNSS', 'COVID-19' or 'SARS-CoV-2', 'the COVID-19 pandemic', 'Internet mapping technologies' or 'WebGIS', and 'review' or 'overview'. Four different sub-topics was then identified based on applications of geospatial techniques including GIS, remote sensing, GPS and Internet mapping technologies in the study of the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, different types of applications of geospatial techniques in the study of COVID-19 were summarised and discussed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Roles of Geographic Information Systems in the COVID-19 fight

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) is a suite of software tools for mapping and analyzing data which is georeferenced (assigned a specific location on the surface of the Earth, otherwise known as geospatial data). GIS can be used to detect geographic patterns in other data, such as disease clusters resulting from toxins, sub-optimal water access, etc. GIS tools can map and visualize the relationship between location coordinates and COVID-19 pandemic cases to map hot spots (15). For instance, to identify the spatio-temporal clustering of COVID-19 hot spots and cold spots in Vietnam using spatial statistics. The local Getis-Ord’s G_i^* statistic was successfully applied to detect hotspots and coldspots of COVID-19 cases in four waves in Vietnam. The results showed that seven hotspots of COVID-19 cases in provinces were detected in areas of high population density in the north-eastern region of Vietnam (Figure 1). Also in Vietnam, the local Moran’s I spatial statistic and Moran scatterplot were successfully employed to identify high-high and low-low clusters and low-high and high-low outliers of COVID-19 cases from a dataset of 10,742 locally transmitted cases in four COVID-19 waves in 63 prefecture-level cities/provinces in Vietnam (16). A Moran's I autocorrelation and spatial cluster analysis for identifying Coronavirus disease COVID-19 using GIS approach was also successfully carried out in Iraq (17). With the advantage of mapping spatial data, GIS has been widely employed to map the COVID-19 vulnerability. For instance, in Palestine, the COVID-19 vulnerability map for the West Bank was successfully developed using the combination of Analytic Hierarchy Process, GIS, multi-criteria decision analysis and some selected potential criteria including population, population density, elderly population, accommodation and food service activities, school students, chronic diseases, hospital beds, health insurance, and pharmacy (18). In India, through geographic information system, attempts were also made to model the COVID-19 vulnerability using an integrated fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making approach, namely fuzzy-analytical hierarchy process and fuzzy-technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution for West Bengal (19). Also with the help of GIS, the analysis of vulnerability to COVID-19 occurrence was also successfully carried out other contries such as in the United States (20), Ethiopia (21), Algeria (22), and México (23). A part from vulnerability assessment, a GIS-based spatial modeling approach was adopted to identify of risk factors contributing to COVID-19 incidence rates in Bangladesh (24), India (25) and other severely COVID-19 affected countries (25–27).

Figure 1. Hotspots and coldspots of locally transmitted cases in four COVID-19 waves in Vietnam (16).

3.2. Roles of Remote Sensing in the COVID-19 fight

Imagery and data collected from space- or airborne camera and sensor platforms. Some commercial satellite image providers now offer images showing details of one-meter or smaller, making these images appropriate for monitoring humanitarian needs and human rights abuses (5), particularly for monitoring natural resources, environment and climate change . Since the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, remote sensing techniques have been widely used to aid governments and other stakeholders in their campaigns against the COVID-19 pandemic by supplying real-time data of on-the-ground conditions to decision makers (28). A recent study of (28) has summarised the roles of remote sensing during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study revealed that remote sensing techniques have been successfully used for (i) real-time decision-making and strategic planning during the pandemic, (ii) investigating it’s impacts on social-economics and environment, and (iii) the study of the epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 (28). One of the first use of remote sensing for real-time decision-making and strategic planning is the assessment of the risk of artisanal fishers to the COVID-19 pandemic in coastal Ghana using an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) (29). Also using UAV, very high-resolution images obtained from two cameras were employed to monitor to monitor social distancing and trace

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COVID-19 infected suspects (30). Remote sensing provides information to support activities affected by the COVID-19 pandemic such as the use of Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 imagery in substituting in-situ surveys for harmful algal blooms in the ocean off the coast in Chile (31). Similar to those reported in a study (28) that remote sensing techniques have been proven their effectiveness in aiding government, private companies, humanitarian, and research organizations in their various activities during the COVID-pandemic. After the COVID-19 outbreak, remote sensing techniques have been also widely applied to assess the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on social-economics and environment. For instances, air pollution was successfully monitored from the space. Recent studies using remotely sensed images have shown that there was a decline in air pollutants from major cities of East Asia, Europe, and the USA (32,33). In India, when measuring the change in PM₁₀ level in the Kolkata metropolitan area, it was found that the level of particulate matter (PM₁₀) has decreased during the COVID-19 induced lockdown (34). In China, PM₁₀ and NO₂ obtained from remotely sensed images were also decreased rapidly from the pre-lockdown stage to the lockdown periods (Figure 2) (35). Similar findings of the improvement of environment quality during the COVID-19 induced lockdown in other contries have been also reported such as lake and surface water quality (36,37), air quality (38,39) and surface urban heat island (40). In the propagation of COVID-19, many studies revealed meteorological variables affect the spread of SARS-CoV-2 (41,42). Data on these meteorological raiables can be obtained by remote sensing techniques. It is therefore, remote sensing such as ground-based, radar, and weather satellite data has been successfully employed in epidemiological studies of COVID-19. For instance, remotely sensed data products was used to investigate the spatial variation in disease transmission rates with local air temperatures, humidity, and air pressure in the United States from NLDAS (43) and ERA5 (44) images, respectively. Also using ERA5, a study of has successfully discovered that low temperature and humidity both correlated to increased disease spread of COVID-19 (45). A part from meteorological variables, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) was proven to have effects on the respiratory system, by increasing the risk for respiratory tract infections (28). A study of (46) has revealed that exposure to NO₂ may be one of the most important environmental determinants for the spread and fatality caused by the COVID-19 disease. Additionally, a positive association between levels of NO₂ levels and subsequent prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 was also detected in northern Italy (47). These above-discussed studies has confirmed the effectiveness of remote sensing in the study of the epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2.

Figure 2. PM₁₀ concentrations in the Guanzhong Basin before and after the COVID-19 outbreak (35).

3.3. Roles of Global Positioning System in the COVID-19 fight

Global Positioning System (GPS) is a network of U.S. Department of Defense satellites which can give precise coordinate locations to civilian and military users with proper receiving equipment. A similar European system called Galileo will be operational within the next several years while a Russian system is functioning but restricted. GPS and GIS applications can provide real-time mapping, tracking and combating COVID-19 pandemic (15). Particularly, GPS data provided by users' smartphones can be analyzed to obtain a verifiable record of individuals' human mobility patterns and help predict the future disease trajectory of COVID-19 such as the identification of hotspots and the social and environmental factors that contribute to the further spread of COVID-19 (15). One key data source has been human mobility which can be collected from geospatial global positioning system data on smartphones that can be used to support efforts to understand the transmission patterns of COVID-19 and to control the effectiveness of public health interventions like contact tracing (48–50). Specifically, GPS location data in mobile phones has been used to inform analysis of COVID-19 pandemic epidemiology (48). GPS location-based social network data can be used to study mobility during crises during the first wave of Covid-19 outbreak and lockdown in Italy (49). GPS data collected via mobile phone apps was used for capture non-pharmaceutical interventions (50). Additionally, a GPS can be used for for contact tracing of infection chains to enhance response to the COVID-19 pandemic (51). Recently, GPS has been used to track the location and also display grid. It is used to

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display to share the location of bus to the nearby hospitals and fire-services through the control room (52). GPS tracking was proposed to monitor the health conditions of the Covid-19 patients and track their real-time location via mobile application (53). Whereas, information on symptom onset and exposure history of the patients was collected by global positioning system (GPS) tracking to investigate possible points of contact or spread of COVID-19 (54). In Korea, the government used GPS records from their cellular phone or credit card records to generate a movement map which was displayed on the Web or notifications and sent to inhabitants in the relevant neighborhoods so they could take additional precaution (55). The cell phone associated with the GPS location data is collected from the COVID-19 subjects to identify COVID-19 infectious and hazardous sites and to detect disease outbreaks (56). Additionally, GPS has been also proven its effectiveness in the COVID-19 fight in other studies (57–60).

3.4. Roles of Internet Mapping Technologies in the COVID-19 fight

Internet Mapping Technologies (IMTs) are software programs like WebGIS, Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform, Google map, Baidu map and web features. These technologies are changing the way geospatial data is viewed and shared. One of the main advantages is that IMTs allow deliver up to date information on the COVID-19 pandemic. It is therefore, IMTs have been widely used in the COVID-19 fight. For instance, in response to this ongoing public health emergency, an online interactive dashboard, hosted by the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD, USA, was developed to visualise and track reported cases of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in real time (Figure 3) (61). Web-GIS maps have been widely used for delivering public information on this fast-moving, epidemiologically complex, and geographically unbounded process (62). A WebGIS for small-scale detection and analysis of COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) cases based on volunteered geographic information was developed for the city of Cologne, Germany (63). When investigating geographical tracking and mapping of coronavirus disease COVID-19/SARS-CoV-2 epidemic and associated events around the world, different types of WebGIS-based mapping such as practical online/mobile GIS and mapping dashboards have been successfully used for tracking the 2019/2020 coronavirus epidemic (7). Also based on WebGIS, a visualization system for COVID-19 simulation has also been designed and developed (64). In Gemany, a Web GIS was developed for small-scale detection and analysis of COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) cases based on volunteered geographic information for the city of Cologne (63). In Italy, the construction of a digital cartography tool as a WebGIS to allow local communities understanding of epidemiological spread is presented (65). In India, a user interactive webgis webpage was designed for decision making and resource allocation during COVID in the Solapur City, Maharashtra, India (66).

Figure 3. Johns Hopkins' coronavirus-tracking map.

A part from WebGIS, other IMTs have been also widely in the COVID-19 fight such as Google Earth Engine platform, Google map and Baidu Map. For instances, Google Earth Engine, a web-based platform to resolve big data problems to enhance the processing of satellite images for large-scale applications (67), has been used for spatio-temporal analysis of air pollutants before and during the first wave COVID-19 outbreak over Turkey (68). In recent years, with the increasing availability of open-source data, more and

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more researchers have used Application Programming Interface (API) of online mapping services, such as the Google Map API and Baidu map API, to acquire the estimated travel distance and time for detecting service areas of various travel modes (69). In Poland, Google map was employed to investigate changes in regional and local mobility patterns during COVID-19 lockdown (70). Baidu Map was also successfully used for mapping the accessibility of medical facilities of Wuhan during the COVID-19 pandemic (71). These IMTs have been also widely used for the COVID-19 fight in other studies (69,72,73).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper summarised and synthesized a wide range of applications offered through geospatial techniques to help address different issues related to the fight of the COVID-19 pandemic. A total of 73 scientific papers have been reviewed. The crucial roles of GIS, Remote Sensing, Global Positioning System and Internet Mapping Technologies in the fight of the COVID-19 pandemic were discussed. This study confirms the effectiveness of geospatial techniques not only in the study of COVID-19 in general, but also in the fight of the pandemic in particular. The value of geospatial technique should increase over time, particularly in the study of such a global pandemic as COVID-19.

DECLARATION BY AUTHORS

Ethical Approval: Approved

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